

NFDI BioMed Interest Group Workshop 2024 Report

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Research data management (RDM) within and for biomedical science is facing a distinct set of technical, regulatory and ethical challenges. To develop a common understanding and joint solutions for these challenges, the biomedical interest group within the German *Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur* (NFDI, National Research Data Infrastructure) was formed in early 2024. This interest group - termed “NFDI BioMed” - assembles the five NFDI consortia whose activities cover, at least partially, biomedical research data: GHGA, NFDI4BIOIMAGE, NFDI4Health, NFDI4Immuno and NFDI4Microbiota.

The first two-day workshop of NFDI BioMed took place in Heidelberg in November 2024 and brought together over 50 members of the five consortia, along with several additional attendees representing external stakeholders. The workshop revolved around two key aims: First, to refine the mutual understanding of key concepts that form the basis of the consortias’ activities and second, to identify topics for practical cooperation within NFDI BioMed. We addressed the first aim via four consecutive “deep dive” sessions, during which we discussed condensed versions of the consortias’ (meta)data models, infrastructure architecture, regulatory aspects and approaches to training. With regard to the second aim, we invited all attendees beforehand to propose use cases, which they would consider to be of boarder interest to NFDI BioMed. During the workshop, we then used a Barcamp format to select and discuss nine of the use cases, with topics ranging from standarding workflows over spatial data and data access management to training of data consumers. Several of these proposals have sparked working groups within NFDI BioMed, which are now meeting on a regular basis. This report is a comprehensive documentation of the workshop and all Barcamp sessions.

Barcamp session reports

Session 06: Interaction with EHDS

The European Health Space (EHDS) is one of the data spaces envisaged by the European Commission in 2020 in its European Strategy for Data¹. In March 2024, the European Parliament and the EU Council agreed on a compromise text² for the Regulation that will establish the EHDS in 2025. The Regulation’s provisions regarding secondary use of health data will (mostly) be applied from 2029 onwards and will require holders of various categories of biomedical data to

¹ [COM/2020/66 final](#)

² [TA-9-2024-0331 EN](#)

make them and their metadata available to the “gatekeepers” within the EHDS infrastructure, the Health Data Access Bodies (HDABs). However, the Regulation also creates a new legal basis to process electronic health data for the purpose of health-related research without having to obtain an informed consent of the data subject, as long as the processing is done within the secure framework of the EHDS.

In this barcamp session we discussed how the individual NFDI BioMed consortia are positioning themselves with regard to EHDS. The discussion was guided by three questions:

- *Existing connections to EHDS:* NFDI4Health is already in discussions with the relevant federal ministries (BMG & BMBF) regarding its role (see below). GHGA is part of the “Modellvorhaben Genomsequenzierung”, where discussions are ongoing whether their existing data can be made available or not (as it has been collected under informed consent and genetic data will likely be exempt from the general opt-out clause). The other three consortia have no existing connections.
- *Plans for integration into EHDS:* All consortia state that most of their partners will likely be Data Holders (DH) and therefore need to take the technical requirement of EHDS into account when defining their research data management strategy. The mandatory support for HealthDCAT-AP that all consortia need to be able to provide is a potential area of collaboration.
- *Potential role within EHDS, other than DH:* NFDI4Health plans become a distributed HDAB (dHDAB) for study and cohort data. Several consortia are currently evaluating a role as intermediation entity (IE), however only if the data holders they serve would be research institutions (this is important as the predominant interpretation of the Regulation text assumes that IEs can only be used by micro and small enterprises, not by larger entities).

Session 09: Federated management of data access

Bio-medical research data can frequently not be made completely open for a variety of reasons, e.g., data privacy, intellectual property, biosafety. However, there is substantial interest in the community to share data with trusted institutions or individual collaborators/applicants via a (federated or centralized) data repository infrastructure. In this session we discussed the current authentication and authorization infrastructure (AAI) that our consortia are using (or are planning to use) to manage user identities and access rights in these repositories. We also asked whether there are specific features that biomedical consortia would need from the IAM4NFDI base service.

In general, all five consortia are using AAIs built on the OIDC or SAML standards, with a slight preference towards OIDC. Two consortia are using LS-Login as community attribute service (CAS), which has close integration with Elixir services e.g. de.NBI compute nodes. One consortium uses Helmholtz ID, which is one of the four IAM4NFDI cAAIs. There seems to be hardly any difference between the functionalities of the systems, but it should be noted that LS-Login has support for tokens. In general, SSO capabilities are considered to be very helpful and convenient from the

user side. Assertions are a big plus of AAI relying on institutional IdP (in contrast to social IdPs like Google). Further notes:

- Important institutions (especially Ressortforschungseinrichtungen like the RKI) are not yet part of the DFN-AAI, leading to a low assertion level for employees who then need to use their private accounts.
- Also UKLs might not be part of DFN (and might not provide university accounts to their employees). Would be nice if accounts could be leveled-up with eHBA authentication.
- Leveling-up of assertion is in general considered to be helpful.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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